

PARTICIPANTS NEEDED

FOR STUDY INVESTIGATING FOOD CHOICE

The study will take 30 minutes to complete. You will be asked to fill some questionnaires and make choices between product images displayed on a screen whilst we track your eye movements.

To take part you need to be aged over 18 and have normal vision or wear single lens glasses

£10 voucher reward

If you are interested or would like more information, please speak to the community researchers or contact:

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